

STONE MONUMENT ENSEMBLES AND THE CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT

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1ST STECCI CONFERENCE:
PRESERVING CULTURAL HERITAGE IN TIMES OF CLIMATE CHANGE

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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STONE CONSERVATION IN AUSTRIA: CLIMATE CHANGE CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIES FOR EARLY DETECTION AND PREVENTION

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This presentation focuses on the protection of stone monuments in Austria in the context of advancing climate change. The weathering processes typically observed on exposed stone objects in Austria are potentially intensified by climatic shifts - particularly by increasing moisture cycles, temperature extremes, and more frequent freeze-thaw events. These factors often accelerate material deterioration and significantly raise the demands placed on the preservation and maintenance of stone heritage.

Austria's geological diversity and its location within a temperate Central European inland climate, characterized by four distinct seasons, have fostered a long-standing tradition of object protection. Many of the protective measures developed in this context—such as temporary coverings, protective roofing, and targeted metal cappings - are gaining renewed relevance in light of the growing frequency of extreme weather events. A key emphasis is placed on the need to develop and implement systematic monitoring strategies as an integral part of conservation practice, enabling early detection of risks and preventive action against damage. Selected case studies from recent decades will illustrate successful applications of protective measures and highlight the interplay between practical conservation efforts and the overarching goals of heritage preservation.

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CARVED IN STONE BUT FADING IN CLIMATE: KÖPPEN CLASSIFICATION AND GIS-BASED ANALYSIS OF STEĆCI NECROPOLISES

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Climate change poses a constant threat to various aspects of our life on Earth, particularly in the fields of natural history and heritage conservation. The integrity of stone constructions is one of the most critical aspects that are jeopardized by these climate changes. Stećci, medieval limestone tombstones from the 12th to 16th centuries, are found across Southeastern Europe, distinguished by intricate carvings and inscriptions. As such, they are inscribed on UNESCO's World Heritage List.

This paper examines ten necropolises Blidinje, Ravanjska Vrata, Radimlja, Križevići, Kopošići, National Museum of Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH), Cista Velika, stećci at the Museum of Croatian Archaeological Monuments in Split (CRO), Mramorje (RS), and Žugića Bare (MNE). This study explores the impact of climate change on the preservation of limestone stećci by analyzing thermo- pluviometric parameters and classifying the sites within the Köppen climate system.

The research highlights regional climate variations affecting limestone deterioration and reveals that most necropolises are located in climate classes C and D, specifically Cfa, Cfb, Csa, and Dfb. GIS-based mapping identifies spatial trends in site-specific vulnerability, providing insights to guide future conservation strategies. By integrating archaeology, climatology, and geospatial data, this study underscores the necessity of adaptive conservation measures to safeguard limestone stećci as an essential part of cultural heritage.

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COMPREHENSIVE CONDITION ASSESSMENT OF STEĆCI AND REFERENCE SITES: METHODOLOGY AND RESULTS FROM THE STECCI PROJECT

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This paper presents the methodology, scope, and key findings of the condition assessment conducted as part of the STECCI project (Horizon Europe), aimed at understanding the current state of limestone monument ensembles—stećci and comparative reference sites—under increasing environmental stress. Fourteen sites across Austria, Malta, Germany, France, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia, and Montenegro were assessed using a suite of non-destructive and minimally invasive techniques: visual inspection and digital damage mapping, Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI), ultrasonic pulse velocity testing, water absorption analysis (Karsten tube and contact sponge), gloss and colorimetric measurements, and petrographic analysis.

Fieldwork was carried out during seven site visits in varying climates and seasons, highlighting methodological challenges and the influence of environmental variability. The assessment revealed a spectrum of deterioration processes—including microkarst formation, surface dissolution, biofilm colonization, cracking, and material loss—closely linked to lithotype, exposure, and maintenance history. The resulting dataset establishes a diagnostic baseline that informs future conservation strategies, and serves as a model for assessing at-risk stone heritage across diverse climatic zones.

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Marija Milchin is a stone conservator, who gained her degree in conservation at the University of Applied Arts Vienna in 2006. After two years at a private conservation company (Atelier Gurtner Wien), she started working at the Institute of Conservation in 2008 on the position of university assistant, teaching theory and practice of stone conservation. At the Institute she is frequently involved in projects concerning cultural heritage in Austria and abroad (Nepal, India, Mongolia, Albania, Croatia etc.). Since 2019 her research focuses on the possibilities for protection for outdoor stone monuments with regards to climate change in the frame of her doctoral thesis.

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Siniša Bizjak is a Croatian stone conservator and restorer with a career spanning over two decades. Born on May 4, 1979, he holds an M.A. in Conservation and Restoration from the Arts Academy in Split and a specialist degree in Stone Conservation from a European center in Venice, Italy. Bizjak currently serves as the Vice Dean for Quality and Development at the University of Split's Arts Academy, where he is also an associate professor specializing in stone conservation and restoration.

Since 2008, he has been a university teacher and a mentor for over 20 bachelor's and master's theses. Before his academic career, he worked as a stone conservator-restorer at the Croatian Conservation Institute from 2004 to 2008. An accomplished scholar, Bizjak has published 15 scientific and professional papers and has been a lecturer at more than 15 scientific conferences. He is also the author or co-author of over 60 projects in the field of stone conservation.

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Katharina Fuchs has been a university assistant at the Institute of Conservation at the University of Applied Arts Vienna since 2018, where she primarily instructs and guides students in the field of stone conservation. She completed her studies there in 2014 with a thesis on the maintenance and care of natural stone objects in the palace complex in Patan, Nepal. Afterward, she mainly worked in stucco and scagliola (stucco marble) conservation, as well as at the Austrian Federal Monuments Authority in the Department of Conservation. Alongside her work at the university, she was also a project manager at a stone conservation company until spring 2021. At the moment she is collaborating with the Faculty of Restoration in Litomyšl to study historical grotto decorations in Austria and the Czech Republic. The publication of her dissertation is currently in preparation.

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ENVIRONMENTALLY SUSTAINABLE APPROACH IN CONSERVING HISTORICAL DWELLING HOSTING ETHNOGRAPHIC MUSEUM IN KAVAJA

LEJLA HADZIC, GABRIELA KRIST

Conservation engaging local knowledge and materials results in low environmental impact and it enhances local employability. The process of conservation of Ethnographic Museum of Kavaja demonstrates the sustainability of such a conservation approach. The Museum is housed in the historical residential dwellings constructed in early 1800. The building is almost entirely authentic, it was built using timber, stone, adobe and rammed earth.

Albania was struck by the earthquake in 2019, and both due to the effects of it as well as long overdue maintenance the building suffered severe damages. In the response to effects of the earthquake, the building underwent a full conservation during which the museum displays were as well re-designed. The conservation relied heavily on engagement of traditional craftsmanship and usage of historical materials. Wherever possible materials were recycled and re-used. The engagement of local craftspeople directly contributed to local job creation, while sourcing of materials such as adobe or timber involved local small producers. Important aspect of the work was the skill transfer and training enabled through workshops on artefact conservation or timber roof repairs.

The Museum is now opened for public, and is attracting local and international visitors, and the long term aim is that Kavaja would feed its future economic development while generating income from enhanced cultural tourism.

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SUSTAINABLE CLIMATE CONTROL STRATEGIES FOR COLLECTIONS IN TIME OF CLIMATE CHANGE

TAHMIDA AFROZE

Museums are energy-intensive buildings and most of the energy consumption is associated with the care of collection. To prevent or minimize climate induced mechanical damage to objects under their care, many museums and galleries have followed a policy of close control of the temperature (T) about 20 or 21 \pm 2°C and relative humidity (RH) value between 50 \pm 5% at the display and storage spaces. These requirements are also specified as conditions in cases of loaning collections between institutions. In most instances, museums and collection storage facilities are designed and engineered to achieve the climate control standards and recommend stability mentioned above through mechanical solutions, which requires a significant amount of energy usage. With technological advancements, these parameters have become attainable, but they may still exceed the financial capacity of many museums and pose environmental sustainability challenges due to the associated carbon footprint. On the other hand, inquiries regarding the suitability of a single set point for various types of collections, building structures, and climatic regions have increased in recent decades. This research is intended to investigate the evolution of environmental guidelines for the preservation of collections and how through the collaborative effort of different professionals involved in the functioning of a museum can help to achieve a balance between preservation and sustainability within a museum setting.

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Tahmida Afroze has a background in architecture and museum studies. She was a graduate intern at the Getty Conservation Institute's Managing Collection Environments (MCE) initiative in 2023-24. She has advised the collection management for the Bengal Foundation, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Focused on heritage and preventive conservation, her research interests are in minimizing energy needs in museum buildings without causing adverse effects to collections. She has a joint master in cultural heritage conservation and management from the Institute of Conservation, University of Applied Arts, Vienna, and Silpakorn University International College, Bangkok, Thailand; a post graduate diploma in museum and gallery practice from University College London, Qatar; and a master in World Heritage and cultural projects from Turin School of Development.

THE CONTRIBUTION OF FIELD-BASED GEOGRAPHY EDUCATION TO THE PRESERVATION OF CULTURAL HERITAGE IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE: THE CASE OF THE VIMINACIUM ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITE

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The vulnerability of cultural heritage due to the effects of climate change represents a major challenge for contemporary society. Education is recognized as a key prerequisite for addressing this issue. Students are introduced to topics related to the preservation and protection of space and cultural heritage as early as in primary education. Particularly important are those curricular contents that emphasize the interdependence of natural, social, and ecological processes. Geography, as a spatial science, enables the implementation of such topics through various approaches, with field-based teaching being especially impactful. Considering the importance of locally grounded examples, this paper proposes a theoretical didactic model that examines the impact of climate change on the archaeological site of Viminacium. Viminacium, an ancient monument of high cultural and historical value, is exposed to climatic, hydrological, and anthropogenic risks (increased precipitation, erosion, flooding, and the effects of industry and mining). The model is based on the principles of active learning and inquiry-based teaching, aiming to develop spatial thinking, ecological values, and awareness of sustainable development among students. Its educational value lies in promoting ecological consciousness by helping students understand the dual role of humans as both contributors to climate change and agents of its mitigation and cultural heritage protection.

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SUSTAINABLE CONSERVATION OF THE SGRAFFITO FACADE OF THE LITOMYŠL CASTLE

ZDEŇKA MÍCHALOVÁ, KATEŘINA KRHÁNKOVÁ, ZUZANA WICHTERLOVÁ,
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The Litomyšl Castle – a UNESCO World Heritage Site – is currently going through a renovation of its facades. Last year, the Faculty of Restoration, University of Pardubice took part in restoring the figural sgraffito in the castle's courtyard, a masterpiece of Czech Renaissance art. What is particularly remarkable is that, unlike the majority of sgraffito-decorated facades, it has never been covered with secondary plaster. In preparation for the restoration, extensive archival research was carried out with the aim of mapping in detail the restoration work done in the past. The research revealed the frequency of restoration work in the 19th and 20th centuries, the changing approach of each generation of conservators, and what influenced these interventions.

Historical research and additional material surveys became the basis for the current restoration work. The consequences of previous interventions could be observed over a longer period of time. Some problems only grew with each restoration, they were pushed forward, and accumulated. The goal of our intervention was to find a sustainable approach. It is necessary to balance prevention, minimal intervention, and sustainable conservation. This is a very difficult task in the case of exterior monuments. Our intervention began with preventive protection, especially against splashing and leaking water. Conservation focused on thorough deep consolidation and injection, with procedures and materials chosen with regard to retreatability. A key step was the use of the Strech-press method to pull the plaster to the surface during injection.

We believe that the current intervention has significantly improved the long-term durability of this valuable exterior sgraffito work.

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GREEN SKILLS IN HERITAGE CONSERVATION: FROM PRACTICE TO RESEARCH AND TEACHING

TANJA KIMMEL, MARIJA MILCHIN

Today, conservation and restoration face not only technological and ethical challenges but also the urgent need to establish sustainable and resource-efficient practices. Green Skills - environmentally friendly expertise and sustainable methods - are increasingly becoming a central component of the professional profile of conservators. But how deeply are they already embedded in practice, education, and research?

By definition, restoration is a sustainable discipline: it preserves, protects, and extends the lifespan of cultural heritage. However, in light of climate change and growing environmental demands, it is essential to understand the effects of climate change on cultural assets, critically assess conservation practices, evaluate existing concepts, and develop new approaches. This presentation highlights examples from both indoor and outdoor contexts to show how conservators are adapting to changing conditions and actively contributing to reducing their ecological footprint.

A particular focus of the presentation is the integration of sustainable skills into research and teaching. This involves not only theoretical foundations but, above all, practical implementation.

Museums, heritage authorities, and the cultural sector as a whole bear a dual responsibility: they safeguard cultural heritage and can simultaneously serve as role models for sustainable action. By systematically integrating Green Skills into practice, research, and education, they contribute not only to climate protection but also to the dissemination of sustainable conservation methods. In doing so, the transition toward resource-conscious and environmentally aware restoration can be actively shaped and firmly anchored for the long term.

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NON-INVASIVE EXTRACTION OF PROTEINACEOUS BINDERS IN PAINTED ARTIFACTS: A PROTEOMIC APPROACH USING COMPOSITE GELLAN GUM

JIN DONG, ZHANYUN ZHU

This study aims to develop a non-invasive extraction method for painted artifacts to prevent the degradation of sampled proteins after their removal from the artifacts, while enhancing the extraction efficiency of aged proteins, thereby contributing to the improved conservation of painted artifacts. The research explores the impact of high-acyl gellan gums, combined with varying concentrations of urea, acetic acid, and Tris, on the extraction of proteinaceous binders in aged specimens. Protein extraction efficiency was assessed through fluorescence quantification and high-performance liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS/MS). The safety of non-invasive extraction methods was evaluated using various techniques, including visual inspection, optical microscopy, color difference analysis, pH testing, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and contact angle measurement. Results demonstrated that gellan gums combined with urea, Tris, and acetic acid significantly improved protein extraction efficiency. Urea, in particular, weakened hydrophobic bonds within proteins and increased the solubility of non-polar molecules, resulting in the highest protein yield. Proteomic analysis revealed that all gellan gum compositions performed well in identifying collagen, unique peptides, sequence coverage, and peptide spectrum matches (PSMs). In terms of safety, the gellan gum mixed with urea showed minimal macroscopic and microscopic effects on the surface integrity, pH, contact angle, color difference, and internal structure of the painted artifact specimens. Based on these findings, gellan gum with 15% urea was identified as the most effective and safest option for non-invasive proteinaceous binder extraction from painted artifacts.

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THERMAL INSULATION OF FACADES OF POST-WAR ARCHITECTURE AND CARE OF EXTERIOR WORKS OF ART IN THE CZECH REPUBLIC

VLADISLAVA ŘÍHOVÁ, IRENA KUČEROVÁ

In socialist Czechoslovakia, a number of works of art related to architecture were created between 1945 and 1989. Their financing was a mandatory part of the budgets of all public buildings. This layer of artwork has been threatened in recent years by facade insulation systems. Some works have disappeared from the public space, others are presented in situ in the “windows” of polystyrene cladding. Others have been dismantled and placed in storage or in museums. The care of post-war works of art is not yet systematic in the Czech Republic.

The registration and recording of information on the condition of post-war works of art is dealt with in the databases Sculptures and Cities and Czech Mosaics. Currently, more than 7,000 art objects (mosaics, reliefs, murals) are presented in them.

The paper will present different approaches to the care of this area of cultural heritage and will focus on the results of the field documentation of works of art.

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SYNTHESIS OF HYDROXYAPATITE NANOPARTICLES FOR CONSOLIDATION OF HISTORIC MARBLE AND LIMESTONE

CHAINA SINGHAL, SATISH CHANDRA PANDEY

Historic structures constructed out of calcareous stones are susceptible to degradation from environmental factors majorly acid rain, necessitating the development of effective conservation strategies. This research addresses the critical need for advanced preservation techniques by investigating the synthesis of hydroxyapatite nanoparticles for application as a consolidant for deteriorated marble. Hydroxyapatite, a calcium phosphate mineral with excellent biocompatibility and chemical similarity to the mineral composition of these stones, presents a promising solution for developing structurally compatible and durable protective treatments. The vulnerability of marble to dissolution by acid rain poses a significant threat to cultural heritage sites globally, leading to granular disaggregation and the phenomenon known as sugaring. Traditional preservation methods often fall short in providing long-term protection without compromising the aesthetic or structural integrity of the stone. The aim of this study is to synthesize hydroxyapatite nanoparticles with controlled morphology and size distribution, and to evaluate their effectiveness in consolidating and protecting marble surfaces against acid attack. We hypothesize that the application of hydroxyapatite nanoparticles will enhance the durability and resistance of these stones, offering a sustainable solution for their long-term preservation. The synthesized nanoparticles will be characterized using a range of techniques, including X-ray diffraction, transmission electron microscopy, and dynamic light scattering, to determine their crystalline structure, particle size, and dispersion properties. Furthermore, the performance of the hydroxyapatite nanoparticle consolidant will be assessed through accelerated weathering tests, including exposure to simulated acid rain and freeze-thaw cycles, to evaluate its ability to mitigate degradation.

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and developing sustainable conservation methodologies and approaches.

LICHEN BIODETERIORATION OF MEGALITHIC HERITAGE IN MANIPUR: AN ASSESSMENT OF RISK AND RESPONSE

SATISH CHANDRA PANDEY, KSHETRIMAYUM KAMALJIT SINGH

Megaliths are large stone structures or monuments constructed by ancient communities for various purposes, including burial practices and the commemoration of significant events. These monuments remain largely neglected, with inadequate conservation efforts leading to their deterioration. This study examines the current condition of megaliths in Manipur, with a particular focus on lichen-mediated deterioration. Many megalithic sites in the state are abandoned and unprotected, making them vulnerable to biological colonization by plants, mosses, fungi, algae, and lichens. This study examines lichen-mediated degradation of megaliths in Manipur, focusing on four sites across Churachandpur and Senapati districts. Lichen samples were collected from Salangthel, Paomata, Pudunamei, and Willong Khullen, alongside uncolonized rock samples for petrographic analysis. Thin Layer Chromatography and Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry were used to analyze lichen chemistry, while Scanning Electron Microscopy with Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy investigated lichen-rock interactions. A total of 22 lichen species were identified, with crustose forms (12 species) being predominant. Rock samples included sandstone and calcareous limestone, categorized into sublithic arenite, subarkose arenite, calcareous limestone, and lithic subarkose. Lichen-induced deterioration was attributed to both physical and chemical mechanisms. Secondary metabolites, such as usnic acid, atranorin, and norstictic acid, along with oxalic and carbonic acids, contributed to mineral breakdown. Scanning electron microscopy revealed calcium oxalate crystals at the lichen-rock interface, indicating chemical interactions. Additionally, mechanical stress from lichen expansion and contraction accelerated physical degradation. The susceptibility of megaliths to lichen-induced weathering depends on mineral composition and lichen species present. Given their cultural significance, preserving these prehistoric structures requires regular monitoring, ecological assessments, and protective measures against anthropogenic disturbances to mitigate further degradation.

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THE INFLUENCE OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON CULTURAL HERITAGE IN THE BORDER AREA OF SERBIA WITH BULGARIA

MARKO SEDLAK, VLADIMIR MALINIĆ

Climatic conditions and climate change are the focus of modern research due to their direct and indirect impact on the lives of the population and economic activity. In this paper, climate changes are presented and the connection with their impact on the cultural heritage in the border area of Serbia with Bulgaria is brought. This paper aims to relate climate changes with their impact on cultural heritage (monumental heritage, events, and traditional activities such as wine cellars in Negotin). The primary task of the work is to identify the trends of the main climatic elements (temperature, precipitation, insolation), the occurrence of tropical days, frosty days, and other extreme climatic phenomena and indicate their potential connection with cultural heritage. Secondary tasks are the identification of the regional distribution of cultural heritage in this territory to spatially analyze the impact of climate on them, the evaluation of the importance of existing cultural values, as well as the analysis of differences in tourist indicators (tourist traffic, length of stay, average number of overnight stays). Sustainable regional development will be presented to establish a balance between the social and economic impact of the climate on cultural assets in this area, as well as the possibility of using cultural values in the function of establishing sustainable communities. In this context, a significant segment of the work will be represented by proposed measures for action on climate change, which are defined in the sustainable development goal 13 (Climate action).

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CLIMATE MEETS POLLUTION: DUAL-MODEL MAPPING OF LIMESTONE SURFACE RECESSION ACROSS BIOGEOGRAPHICAL EUROPE

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Increasingly exposed to the combined impacts of climate change and air pollution, limestone monuments are undergoing accelerated material degradation. This study applies a dual-model approach to quantify limestone surface recession at 15 heritage sites between 1992 and 2023, using two dose–response functions: Lipfert (focused on precipitation-driven acid dissolution) and Kucera (multi-pollutant based). Sites were selected to represent a broad spectrum of climatic conditions, pollutant exposure levels, and biogeographical zones across Europe, including continental, alpine, and Mediterranean regions, both urban and rural contexts. These include Sarajevo, Križevići, Kopošići, Blidinje, Ravanjska Vrata (BIH), Mramorje (RS), Split and Velika Cista (CRO), Žugića Bare (MNE), Mdina Rabat (Malta), Hundskirche (AT); Unsleben and Kleinbardorf Jewish Cemeteries (DE); and Caen (FR). Harmonized environmental datasets (SO₂, NO_x, PM₁₀, temperature, and precipitation) reveal divergent model sensitivities: Lipfert estimates are higher in humid, high-rainfall zones (Žugića Bare), while Kucera better reflects pollutant-driven deterioration in urban contexts (Sarajevo, Mdina Rabat). These findings highlight site-specific degradation dynamics shaped by climate and air quality interactions. This evidence-based approach supports integrated risk mapping and the development of adaptive conservation policies at regional and European levels.

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CONSERVING OC EO CULTURAL HERITAGE UNDER CLIMATE STRESS: A CASE STUDY FROM THE MEKONG DELTA, VIETNAM

QUANG KHANH NGUYEN

The Mekong Delta in southern Vietnam is increasingly affected by environmental problems caused by climate change, such as rising sea levels, saltwater intrusion, land subsidence, and more frequent extreme weather events. These changes pose a serious threat to the Oc Eo heritage sites, which contain significant archaeological remains of an ancient civilization that flourished in the region from the 1st to 7th centuries AD.

This study looks at the current state of these sites and how climate change is damaging them. It also finds weaknesses in how they are currently being protected. Based on this, the study suggests ways to improve conservation efforts that are more suitable for the changing climate. These ideas can be useful for other places in Asia dealing with similar problems.

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CLIMATE CHANGE AND ITS IMPACT ON STEĆCI IN THE TERRITORY OF BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

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The analysis of climate change in Bosnia and Herzegovina is based on monitoring two fundamental climatic elements: air temperature and annual precipitation at the Bjelave meteorological station (Sarajevo). The Sarajevo meteorological station holds a continuous and homogeneous record of observations for these two climatic elements spanning 137 years (from 1888 to 2025), providing a highly representative dataset for tracking climate change and fluctuations in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Particular attention will be given to the past 30 years, during which climate change trends have been especially pronounced. The main characteristic of the thermal-pluviometric regime is warming and humid stagnation. The average annual temperature over the entire instrumental period is 9.8°C, with a linear warming trend of 1.7°C. The average secular value of the annual precipitation sum is 918.8 mm, with a slight increase of 14 mm. Using spatial modeling based on thermal and pluviometric changes, the areas in Bosnia and Herzegovina most vulnerable to climate impacts, such as landslides, floods, and wildfires is identified. These models will be compared with the distribution of stećci to identify the most affected sites. This analysis, grounded in the region's physical-geographical features, offers a valuable case study for Southeastern Europe and contributes to a broader understanding of climate change impacts on cultural heritage across Europe.

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STONE DURABILITY UNDER CLIMATIC INFLUENCES: A CASE STUDY OF THE YUGOSLAV MONUMENT AT THE MAUTHAUSEN MEMORIAL

DESIMIR TANOVIĆ, ANA TKALAC, DUNJA SVILAR DUJKOVIĆ

The Yugoslav monument within the Mauthausen Memorial was erected in 1958 to honor the Yugoslav victims. The design specified the use of home materials, marble and granite, for the monument. It featured 8-meter-high two obelisks, and a "sarcophagus" constructed from eleven marble panels, all made from white marble sourced from Venčac. All materials were prepared and produced in Yugoslavia. In response to a report submitted by the diplomatic mission of the Republic of Serbia in Austria regarding the deteriorating condition of the marble columns, the Institute for the Protection of Cultural Monuments of Serbia initiated an investigation in 2024. This research included collecting data from archival documents dating back to the original memorial's construction in 1957 and detailed comparison with the monument's current state. This study presents a comparative analysis of the properties of the material at the time of construction and its current condition, after 68 years of exposure to climatic factors and static stability. The Institute for Materials in Belgrade conducted examinations of the stone samples in 1957 and again in 2024.

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COHESION AND SUSTAINABILITY OF CULTURAL HERITAGE IN THE FACE OF THE CHALLENGES OF CLIMATE CHANGE

NEVENA ĆURČIĆ, VESELA RADOVIĆ

Preservation of cultural heritage is an important task for every country. Influences from the natural environment exert a great influence on monuments and architectural heritage, even causing permanent degradation and destruction. The negative impact of external influences is reflected in the action of: floods, fires, landslides, earthquakes, strong storms and high winds, rise in pollutants and bio-infestation, etc. The subject of this study is the negative natural impacts associated with climate change and the consequences on cultural heritage, with reference to Serbia. The goal of the study is to answer the questions of the social significance of heritage today and whether it is sufficiently recognized by public policy makers as a potential in cultural tourism through examples of successfully implemented rehabilitation, conservation and restoration of cultural heritage. The methodology applied in the research is based on the application of multivariable content analysis of secondary data sources. The results indicate that the sustainability of cultural heritage must be linked to a strong cohesion of professional knowledge, cultural potential and general community involvement. In the future, the sustainability of cultural heritage will pose increasing challenges in the fight for preservation in the face of growing extreme factors from nature. Also, climate and socio-economic changes together will have a far greater effect on the preservation of cultural heritage, compared to climate changes considered individually.

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ACCESSING VULNERABILITY: THE IMPACT OF EXTREME WEATHER EVENTS ON CULTURAL HERITAGE SITES IN SERBIA

VESELA RADOVIĆ, NEVENA ĆURČIĆ

This article delves into the crucial conference theme of the impacts of climate change on tangible cultural heritage and the assessment of its vulnerability. Drawing inspiration from the significant legacy of Victor Hugo, whose renowned novel *Notre Dame de Paris* poignantly underscores the importance of Gothic architecture in Paris, the piece reflects on the present-day dilemmas surrounding cultural heritage. In the 21st century, a tendency toward commodification often threatens these historical treasures. Despite this, many individuals yearn to cultivate connections with the past, reveling in the unique sensation of stepping into history when they enter ancient buildings. Yet, the preservation of such heritage is met with numerous adversities. Some threats are visible, arising from misguided ideologies that seek to erase our historical legacy. Others, more insidious, stem from the realities of global climate change—an imposing challenge that can render preservation efforts increasingly futile. Defined both mathematically and physically, extreme weather events disrupt established climatic patterns, manifesting as floods, droughts, heat waves, hurricanes, and storms. Each event has a distinct impact on cultural heritage, varying based on the specific vulnerabilities and resilience of the sites involved. This article employs social science methodologies to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the vulnerability and adaptability of selected cultural heritage sites in Serbia to these extreme weather events. The conclusions provide actionable recommendations for policymakers, emphasizing strategic approaches to mitigate risks, minimize costly restoration efforts, and effectively safeguard our invaluable cultural heritage from the looming threat of potential destruction.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF PARADATA IN DIGITAL CULTURAL HERITAGE ACQUISITION

ANTHONY CASSAR

As digital acquisition techniques in cultural heritage advance in complexity and precision, there is a growing demand for transparent, reproducible, and future-proof methodologies. Central to this evolution is the integration of paradata - the documentation of decisions, processes, tools, and human interventions that shape the creation of digital heritage assets. Drawing on recent insights from the Horizon Europe STECCI project, this paper explores the transformative role of paradata in redefining acquisition strategies for the digitisation of the stećci medieval tombstones.

Following a pivotal 2024 training programme in Cyprus, organised under the UNESCO Chair on Digital Cultural Heritage, our team fully embedded paradata into our acquisition workflows. This led to a fundamental rethinking of our methodologies: from pre-planning, structured data collection, and workflow design to in-field paradata capture and post-processing documentation. This approach has allowed us to systematically record not only what was digitised and how, but also who was involved, under what environmental and operational conditions, and with which interpretative choices, ensuring traceability, scholarly accountability, and long-term data reusability.

This methodology directly aligns with the recommendations of the European Commission's Study on Quality in 3D Digitisation of Tangible Cultural Heritage, which highlights the importance of transparency, metadata, and process documentation in creating high-quality and interoperable digital assets (European Commission, 2021). More significantly, the integration of paradata has become a foundational step in advancing from conventional Digital Twin models toward the concept of the Memory Twin - a more holistic digital surrogate that encompasses not only the physical and spatial dimensions of heritage, but also its intangible, historical, and cultural significance. By embedding paradata at every stage of the acquisition process, we are establishing a robust framework that supports both rigorous academic use and innovative, multi-layered engagement with heritage narratives. This paper presents the STECCI case studies as a model for paradata-driven acquisition and proposes it as a strategic enabler for sustainable and meaningful digital heritage ecosystems.

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MULTI-MODAL NEURAL RENDERING FOR 3D SURFACE RECONSTRUCTION OF STEĆCI TOMBSTONES

LUKA ŠKERJANEC, SAŠA ČAVAL

Neural rendering techniques have advanced significantly in recent years and are rapidly gaining traction in cultural heritage applications. Approaches such as Neural Radiance Fields, Gaussian Splatting, and other multi-modal methods like DUS3R, offer promising complements to traditional Structure-from-Motion photogrammetry.

In this study, we focus on the large-scale digitization of medieval stećci tombstones scattered throughout the Western Balkans. Most were carved from the local soft limestone, which over centuries of exposure to wind, rain, and temperature shifts has gradually erased fine bas-relief ornamentation and rendered once-clear inscriptions faint or entirely unreadable. This widespread surface degradation not only obscures the aesthetic and symbolic significance of the tombstones but also risks losing the historical narratives they bear. By applying precise, high-resolution 3D digitization techniques, we can recover these lost details, capturing every subtle contour and fragment of inscription before they vanish forever.

We present a comparative evaluation of several multi-modal neural rendering pipelines, examining each method's reconstruction accuracy, fidelity to surface detail, and suitability for high-throughput digitization. By highlighting the strengths and limitations of these approaches, we demonstrate their potential to preserve, analyze, and share the unique funerary art of the stećci.

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3D DOCUMENTATION OF STEĆCI USING HIGH-RESOLUTION HANDHELD SCANNERS AND CLOSE-RANGE PHOTOGRAMMETRY FOR CULTURAL HERITAGE PRESERVATION

IVAN MARIĆ, FRAN DOMAZETOVIĆ, ANTE ŠILJEG, AIDA AVDIĆ MARIĆ, MARIO KATIĆ

Stećci, the medieval tombstones found throughout the Western Balkans, represent a unique cultural and historical heritage of Southeast Europe, recognized by UNESCO for their exceptional artistic and cultural value. Despite their significance, many stećci sites remain underdocumented, particularly those located in less accessible or rural areas. This study aims to contribute to the digital preservation of three stećci sites by applying high-resolution 3D recording technologies. The selected sites include the relatively well-known Crlivički stećci i bunari site near Imotski (Croatia), the prominent site at Blidinje Nature Park, and a lesser-known, scarcely documented site near Vareš (Bosnia and Herzegovina).

For all three locations, data acquisition will be conducted using the Artec Eva structured-light handheld scanner—a mobile, high-accuracy 3D scanning system widely used in cultural heritage documentation. Additionally, two of the tombstones will be recorded using a Nikon D5300 DSLR camera equipped with an AF-S DX Nikkor 18–105mm lens, along with a DJI Matrice 300 UAV with a P1 camera, to generate 3D models via structure-from-motion (SfM) photogrammetry. This combination of various sensors will allow for a comparative assessment of the resulting models in terms of geometric accuracy, level of detail, and suitability for various applications. The integration of structured-light scanning and photogrammetry offers an opportunity to evaluate the advantages and limitations of each method within fieldwork conditions typical of remote stećci sites. This research enhances the digital archive of stećci and presents a methodological framework for efficient, field-based heritage recording. It also assesses the impact of human-driven preservation efforts on the structural condition of stećci monuments, in comparison to natural degradation processes occurring without human intervention.

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USE OF PHOTOGRAMMETRY FOR THE SURVEY AND CONSERVATION OF THE SIR ROBERT CLAYTON STATUE

ALBERT TRABY

This project explores the role of photogrammetry in the assessment of cultural heritage, focusing on the Grade I listed statue of Sir Robert Clayton at St Thomas' Hospital, London. Carved in 1701 by the eminent Anglo-Dutch sculptor Grinling Gibbons (1648–1721) the statue represents one of the few surviving examples of Gibbons' work in stone. Its continued public display became a subject of debate due to Clayton's involvement in slavery prompting an independent consultation by Guy's & St Thomas' Foundation in the wake of the 2020 Black Lives Matter protests. While the statue was ultimately retained in situ with context interpretation panels, the foundation commissioned to Cliveden Conservation a detailed conservation survey to assess its deteriorating condition.

Central to the conservation strategy was the integration of high-resolution photogrammetry which enabled the creation of an accurate 3D digital model of the statue. This model provided the basis for printed elevation sheets used on-site to annotate visual observations in detail, mapping conditions such as erosion, fissures, sugaring, staining, and historic repairs. Combined with other digital survey tools like USB microscopy, the annotated visual data allowed for a comprehensive and accessible record of the statue's surface condition. Given the decision by stakeholders to retain the statue in its current outdoor location—exposed to the elements and situated near the River Thames—this highly detailed visual record will be critical for future comparisons, helping to track deterioration over time and assess what may have been lost. This case study demonstrates how digital tools can improve conservation planning, especially when preserving historically significant and politically sensitive public monuments.

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DIGITAL STRATEGIES FOR THE DOCUMENTATION AND INTERPRETATION OF MONUMENTAL FUNERARY LANDSCAPES: THE MONUMENTAL CEMETERY OF PERUGIA

ELEONORA DOTTORINI

Funerary landscapes are a complex form of cultural heritage, where a strong monumental component intertwines with tangible and intangible values, creating a distinctive cultural fabric. Beyond their architectural and artistic significance, they embody beliefs, ritual practices, collective identities, and urban transformations. As places of memory and cultural landscapes, monumental cemeteries are key identity landmarks in Europe and the focus of growing initiatives for conservation, sustainable enhancement, and public communication. Digital technologies play a crucial role in these processes, enabling knowledge, documentation, interpretation, and dissemination, while offering strategies to address the challenges posed by climate change.

Within this framework, the ongoing doctoral research in Civil and Environmental Engineering at the University of Perugia focuses on the Monumental Cemetery of the city. Inaugurated in 1849 on a site used for burials since the Etruscan-Roman period, it remains active and represents a deeply stratified urban funerary landscape. My presentation illustrates the methodology and development of a holistic digital model integrating the site's multiple cultural dimensions through an interdisciplinary approach. It combines digital surveys, archival sources, visual repertoires, and participatory content, aligning with European strategies for the sustainable valorization of monumental heritage and contributing to the UN SDGs.

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CO-CREATION AND CITIZEN SCIENCE: COMMUNITY-BASED IMPACT STRATEGIES FOR A SUSTAINABLE ECOSYSTEM OF STEĆCI

PAMELA BARTAR, GABOR SZÜDI

The input presents the co-creation process and the achievements of the STECCI project task Bringing STECCI Labs to Life working with Community-Based Impact Strategies for a Sustainable Ecosystem of Stećci within the Horizon Europe funded project. The results of three social labs and two citizen science hubs comprise recommendations for educational programs and cultural policy making, strategic ideas for cultural tourism in stećci regions and an initial concept for a European Stećci (Cultural) route with an initial route in BH. Furthermore, the input explains tailor-made experimental methods for CH citizen science in the context of social science and humanities (SSH) including participatory storytelling and design thinking as well as Art-of-Hosting approaches and STEM and SciArt experiments as part of science education. The overarching aim of these activities was to generate site-specific findings and solutions to local challenges in preservation while contributing to the co-creation of digital content for the STECCI virtual tours and an educational game. The labs supported the development of a pilot medieval heritage tourism concept such as the route linking the necropolis of Kopošići with the old Bosnian town of Dubrovnik via Ilijaš, integrating cultural and natural heritage. In the general, the stakeholder engagement within STECCI project comprised 14 public events and workshops for co-creation, which were implemented in five STECCI pilots located in Bosnia & Herzegovina, Montenegro, Croatia, Serbia and Germany. The labs and citizen science activities implemented small and medium-scale citizen science and co-creation activities and laid a solid basis for the out-reach activities in the STECCI project and beyond project end.

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VALUING HERITAGE IN A CHANGING CLIMATE THROUGH WILLINGNESS TO PAY AND ECONOMIC VALUATION OF STEĆCI PRESERVATION IN MONTENEGRO

KRUNA RATKOVIĆ, NATAŠA KOVAČ, MILIKA MIRKOVIĆ, VOJIN GOLUBOVIĆ

This paper presents the methodological framework and preliminary findings of a country-level economic analysis conducted in Montenegro under the Horizon Europe STECCI project. Focusing on the valorisation and preservation of stećci, medieval tombstones recognised as UNESCO World Heritage sites, the study examines how contingent valuation methods and willingness-to-pay surveys can be used to quantify the economic and social value of heritage conservation in the context of climate change.

Using a pre- and post-lecture survey approach, the research measures changes in WTP after an awareness-raising intervention about climate-induced risks to cultural heritage. A targeted sample of residents, tourists, and cultural heritage stakeholders participated in structured surveys, providing insights into their motivations, attitudes, and financial commitment to heritage preservation.

Statistical methods were employed to analyse the data and identify key determinants of WTP variations. The findings from Montenegro highlight both the tangible and intangible benefits of stećci preservation, underscoring its potential to contribute to sustainable tourism and regional development.

This paper demonstrates how economic valuation tools can support evidence-based cultural policies and strengthen community engagement in heritage protection under the pressures of a changing climate.

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GLOBAL STANDARDS, LOCAL REALITIES: A CRITICAL STUDY OF UNESCO'S HERITAGE POLICIES IN THAILAND

VICTORIA MICHLMAYER

This paper examines conflicts between international heritage standards, particularly UNESCO frameworks—and local conservation practices in Southeast Asia, with a focus on Thailand. Using critical conservation theory and postcolonial approaches, the research questions how material authenticity and formal expertise dominate global heritage management while marginalizing local knowledge. Through a case study of Ayutthaya Historical Park and Wat Chaiwatthanaram, the study shows how standardized restoration disrupts living heritage and ongoing religious practices. While climate change pressures demand urgent action, they often lead to top-down interventions that ignore local ways of building resilience and spiritual values. By questioning whether conventional restoration is truly sustainable, this paper argues for community-based, adaptive approaches that respect cultural knowledge and respond to both environmental challenges and power imbalances.

These findings support the STECCI project's call for interdisciplinary methods in heritage conservation and offer insights for creating inclusive heritage policies that work across different cultural settings.

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AESTHETIC, PARTICIPATORY AND SUSTAINABLE? THE NEW EUROPEAN BAUHAUS FOR CULTURAL HERITAGE RESEARCH AND GOVERNANCE

PAMELA BARTAR, PHILIPP BRUGNER

The New European Bauhaus is an initiative by the EC to create beautiful, sustainable, and inclusive spaces. This includes monuments, buildings, curated landscapes. The input uses the NEB idea and reflects the initiative as a thinking framework that can be helpful in the research, management and governance of tangible CH. In this reading, NEB promotes an approach that combines aesthetics with sustainability and social inclusion. Incorporating NEB into preservation and valorisation plans can contribute to socially inclusive forms of research and CH management or decision-making and thus holds potential for the deep scaling of democratisation in a socio-political sense (Human 2015). So, NEB can empower communities to collaborate on projects, which reflect both, Europe's diverse history and contemporary innovation – without neglecting social or environmental aspects.

Our conclusions are inspired by the interim results of the European project INHERIT (2023-2027) and can be transferred to all forms of tangible CH. The input contributes to an understanding of social innovation that integrates creativity, aesthetic or beautifulness: beautiful environments can improve the wellbeing or promote a shared understanding and the participation in decision-making processes (McCarthy & Wright 2024). After an introduction to the NEB framework, the input will present how NEB fosters the co-creation and participatory research in the INHERIT project and its Multi-Stakeholder Forum.

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TOURISMOLOGICAL VALORIZATION OF THE MEDIEVAL TOMBSTONES (STECĆI) FROM JAJCE, BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

DRAGAN GLAVAŠ, EDIN BUJAK

The area of Jajce stands as an exceptional example of the organic link between human and natural heritage, revealing eight historical layers within a relatively small space. Medieval monolithic tombstones (stećci) play a significant role in Jajce's rich tangible heritage. They were created from the 12th to the 16th century, while they were most intensively hewed during the 14th and 15th century.

Stećci present an exceptional testimony to the medieval culture of Southeastern Europe that was developed within a unique historical context in an area where medieval cultures and traditions of the European West, East and South meet. Since 2016, twenty-eight sites, located in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia, Montenegro and Croatia, have been inscribed on the UNESCO World Heritage List. Stećci from the area of Jajce stand out due to their abundance, preservation and specific type of ornamentation.

This paper seeks to valorize 31 stećci necropolises in Jajce, 5 of which have the highest state protection status, using the Hilary du Cros valorization model. This approach will determine values for market attractiveness, importance for tourism product design, cultural/natural significance, and site suitability for tourism development. By affirming stećci as crucial resources for selective tourism, the paper aims to promote their formal protection and the mitigation of negative impacts, notably climate change.

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SWISS CHALLENGES ON CLIMATE RESILIENT BUILT HERITAGE

NINA MEKACHER, GIACINTA JEAN, FRANCESCA PIQUÉ, CRISTIAN SCAPOZZA

In december 2024 a four-year project entitled “climate-resilient built heritage” was launched in switzerland aimed at developing strategies and knowledge to support architectural heritage in successfully responding to the challenges of climate change. Led by prof. Dr. Nina mekacher from bern university applied sciences, and conducted in collaboration with the university of applied sciences and arts of southern switzerland and the university of applied sciences and arts of western switzerland, the project emphasizes a transdisciplinary approach that bridges research and society. The research operates on four levels: first, gathering data to identify the main climate-related changes affecting heritage sites; second, formulating indications for preventive actions to enhance resilience; third creating expert and lay networks; fourth formulating policy objectives. A survey allowed to contact interested parties who are willing to discuss problems and share experiences. Several case studies, across various climatic regions, building types, and materials will be analysed. The key challenges to address are related to the use of existing and future climate data to predict how immovable cultural heritage will be affected, to assess risk and vulnerability, planning effective interventions, and producing accessible data for stakeholders. Ultimately, the project aims to generate practical knowledge and actionable recommendations, fostering an integrated, evidence- based approach.

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ON-SITE EVALUATION OF THE PRESERVATION OF HUMAN BONES UNEARTHED IN XI 'AN AREA

LING XUE, XI YIHANG

Ancient human bones are common and important research objects in archaeological research. Through the analysis and research of the unearthed ancient human bones, we can not only understand the history of human evolution, understand the genetic characteristics of human beings, infer the lifestyle and environmental adaptability of the ancestors, but also reveal the precious information of ancient human beings in social structure, cultural customs, diet and health, which is helpful to reconstruct ancient history and provide important reference for us to understand ourselves. Therefore, this study aims to establish an on-site assessment method for the preservation of unearthed human bones suitable for archaeological excavation sites. Taking the human bones unearthed in the archaeological site as the research object, on the basis of clarifying the main factors affecting the preservation status of the unearthed human bones, the evaluation index system of the preservation status of the unearthed human bones was formulated by establishing the evaluation index based on the characteristics of the bone body and the quality of the buried environment. By selecting the data collection method suitable for archaeological site work, the index information reflecting the preservation status of unearthed human bones is obtained. Based on the entropy weight TOPSIS method, an on-site evaluation model for the preservation status of archaeological unearthed human bones was designed. It was successfully applied to the archaeological excavation site of Xipo Village Cemetery in Hui District and the archaeological excavation site of Tuanjie Village Cemetery in Weiyang District in Xi 'an. The evaluation of the preservation status of unearthed human bones effectively verified the scientific nature of the evaluation process, the accuracy of the evaluation method and the rationality of the evaluation model. The research results not only provide a basis for archaeologists to understand the preservation status of unearthed human bones in time, so as to take targeted protection and treatment methods, but also have fundamental significance for promoting the preventive protection of cultural relics.

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URGENT DOCUMENTATION AND PRESERVATION STRATEGIES FOR KERALA'S OUTDOOR TEMPLE MURALS: CHALLENGES AND CASE STUDIES FROM SOUTH INDIA

MOUPI MUKHOPADHYAY

Kerala, in South India, is home to a rich tradition of outdoor temple murals, most often painted on lime plaster over stone or masonry structures. Exposed to a hot, humid climate, many murals are deteriorating rapidly. Unrestored murals retain original materials and offer critical insights into historical techniques, but repainting—though culturally meaningful—and the demolition of older structures to build new ones pose significant threats in addition to climate. Based on the documentation of five temples, this paper highlights the urgency of recording unrestored murals before they are lost. It discusses challenges particular to documenting these temple sites in Kerala and argues for scalable, database-driven strategies that prioritize timely documentation to support preservation and future research.

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CARVED IN STONE, CHALLENGED BY CHANGE: PARTICIPATORY PERSPECTIVES ON THE FUTURE OF STEĆCI

AMINA SIVAC, NUSRET DREŠKOVIĆ, SAIDA IBRAGIĆ, EDIN BUJAK, EDIN HRELJA, MUNIBA OSMANOVIĆ

This paper presents findings from a participatory workshop held in Sarajevo in May 2024, focused on stećci—medieval tombstones characteristic of the cultural landscape of southeastern Europe and inscribed on the UNESCO World Heritage List. The workshop applied the World Café method to enable focused discussion among participants from academia, public institutions, civil society, and the tourism sector, following the quadruple helix model of stakeholder engagement.

Participants discussed six main topics: the effects of climate change on stećci, the cultural and symbolic meanings of these monuments, the role of local communities in their protection, practical forms of participation, existing barriers, and tourism-related opportunities. Responses were analysed using basic qualitative statistical methods, including thematic coding and frequency analysis, to identify recurring themes and shared concerns. The workshop served as a platform to express practical suggestions, local viewpoints, and community-driven priorities in an open group setting.

Although exploratory in nature, the results point to the relevance of participatory approaches in responding to practical heritage issues in the context of climate change, particularly in areas where formal mechanisms of protection remain limited or inconsistent.

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THE TOURISM POTENTIAL OF THE CULTURAL AND HISTORICAL HERITAGE OF THE PAVLOVIĆ LAND: A PROPOSAL FOR A CULTURAL ROUTE FOR THE PROMOTION AND PRESERVATION OF HERITAGE

MARIANA LUKIĆ TANOVIĆ, SANDA ŠUŠNJAR, MILKA GRMUŠA, JELENA GOLIJANIN, MITAR KRSMANOVIĆ, BOJAN KRUNIĆ, ALEKSANDAR MILEKIĆ, RADE IVANOVIĆ

The cultural and historical heritage of the medieval Pavlović noble family represents a latent potential for tourism development. Integrating this heritage into the tourism offer holds multifaceted importance—not only for tourism development, but also for the promotion, protection, and preservation of cultural heritage. This research begins with the hypothesis that it is possible to develop a cultural-tourism route based on the legacy of the Pavlović noble family. Furthermore, it explores the possibility of inter-municipal cooperation in the field of tourism, which could lead to cohesion and the creation of an integrated tourism offer. The Land of the Pavlović family, a medieval feudal domain in present-day Bosnia and Herzegovina, stretched from the watershed between the Bosna and Krivaja rivers in the north to the Drina and Lim rivers in the south. The remains of numerous fortifications built by the Pavlović family are still present—some better preserved than others—but most remain largely unexplored and forgotten. This area also contains a significant number of medieval necropolises marked by stećci tombstones. The aim of this paper is to identify and evaluate the significance of the cultural and historical heritage of the Pavlović family and to propose a cultural route. One of the contemporary trends in the development of heritage tourism is the design and presentation of specialized thematic cultural-tourism routes. Such approaches help connect related heritage sites and destinations, fostering their development, encouraging intercultural dialogue, expanding knowledge, increasing visibility, and enabling the protection of cultural heritage.

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THE INFLUENCE OF ALTITUDE ON THE PRESERVATION OF STEĆAK TOMBSTONES IN THE TUZLA CANTON

EDIN HADŽIMUSTAFIĆ

The subject of research in this paper is the preservation of stećak tombstones in correlation with altitude in the Tuzla Canton. Tuzla Canton is located in the northeastern part of Bosnia and Herzegovina, with an area of 2,649 km², divided into 13 municipalities. The aim of the paper is to analyze the impact of altitude on the preservation of stećak tombstones, or whether altitude is the only factor that affects their preservation. Temperatures decrease with altitude, and the climate is also harsher at higher altitudes. In the Tuzla Canton, a total of 177 necropolises with 1,517 stećak tombstones were analyzed. Necropolises where tombstones were moved from their original locations, necropolises with one stećak tombstone, and stećak tombstones that were damaged by people were excluded from the analysis. The selected tombstones were in poor condition, more eroded, and damaged by climatic factors. This paper analyzes 809 stećak tombstones located in 101 necropolises in 10 municipalities of the Tuzla Canton. The necropolises are located in a range of 103 m up to 1,010 m above sea level. Stećak tombstones data was collected in the field, a relational database was created, which enabled further statistical analysis. The locations and elevations of the necropolises were collected with a GPS device. The database has been integrated into geographic information systems for further geospatial analysis and obtaining new information about these unique Bosnian and Herzegovinian tombstones.

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PREPAREDNESS IN CONSERVATION PRACTICE: LOCAL ADAPTATIONS OF GLOBAL FRAMEWORKS

PRATHAMESH PAWAR, PORNGANOK SADAKORN

The flash floods in 2024 and the earthquake in 2025 in Thailand have underscored the urgent need for disaster preparedness in the field of conservation of cultural heritage. These events exposed significant risks monuments and collections and emphasised the importance of proactive, preventive planning.

This research focuses on practical measures that conservators can take in advance to reduce potential damage to collections. It explores key areas such as risk assessment, collection prioritisation, emergency handling protocols, and institutional coordination. Drawing from both local case experiences and international conservation frameworks, the study proposes a simple, adaptable preparedness measures designed for use in museums, galleries, and storage facilities. By emphasising readiness over reaction, the research encourages conservators to take an active role in strengthening the resilience of the collections under their care.

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INTEGRATING CULTURAL HERITAGE IN CLIMATE POLICY: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES IN KOSOVO

ARIAN TAHIRI

Climate change increasingly threatens ecosystems, economies, and cultural heritage, particularly in Kosovo, a nation grappling with enduring political and socio-economic challenges. This paper investigates the current state of climate policy in Kosovo, focusing on the integration of cultural heritage within climate adaptation and risk management strategies. Specific objectives include assessing the effectiveness of existing frameworks and identifying critical gaps. Although Kosovo has made notable progress in aligning with EU environmental frameworks, challenges persist, including the absence of localized adaptation tools and funding. In ethnically divided areas like Kosovska Mitrovica, interethnic tensions complicate preservation efforts, leading to disputes over religious and historical sites. Budget constraints and Kosovo's exclusion from organizations like UNESCO further impede resource access. The study proposes opportunities for integrating heritage protection into climate planning, emphasizing community-driven initiatives and international collaboration. Ultimately, it underscores the urgent need for comprehensive strategies to safeguard Kosovo's cultural identity against ongoing environmental changes.

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